

Business Strategy to Increase Sales Performance: Case Study of a Mineral Water Product in Indonesia

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ABSTRACT: Currently, people in Indonesia are starting to become aware of consuming proper drinking water so the demand for proper drinking water increases every year. This is an opportunity for Club mineral water to meet market demand. Club's drinking water brand has started to gain public attention, as shown by the Club's brand being included in the category of five bottled drinking water based on consumer choice according to Indonesia's Top Brand data. Even so, the Club has the lowest market share percentage when compared to its four competitors. Furthermore, looking at the internal sales performance of the Indofood CBP's group, sales of the beverage division were smaller than other divisions. This shows that the Club needs to analyze its strategy to improve its sales performance so the company can become a leader in its market. This study further analyzes how the company runs its business from an external and internal perspective. This study uses external analysis such as PESTEL analysis, Porter's five forces, consumer analysis, and competitor analysis. Moreover, there are also internal analyses such as analysis of the company's core competencies, resource-based analysis, and VRIO. Then a further analysis was conducted by using a SWOT analysis to determine the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats to the Club's mineral water products. This study uses qualitative and quantitative methods using a survey of Club mineral water customers. The researcher also analyzed the position of the Club's mineral water compared to its business competitors in terms of sales, followers on Instagram social media, frequencies of Instagram posting, and how competitors use digital media. After that, the TOWS matrix will help the Club's mineral water develop its business and sales. The recommendations given include that the company should know its core competencies to develop, makes product innovations that are different from its competitors, improve the way product promotions are delivered, and optimizes digital media as a sales tool. Strategy implementation in the form of a Gantt chart is made based on these recommendations so that PT ICBP Club could implement it properly.

KEYWORDS: Business Strategy, Competitive Advantage, Bottled Drinking Water, FMCG, Marketing Strategy, Mineral Water, Market Development.

INTRODUCTION

The Indonesian Consumers Foundation (YLKI) stated that the consumption of bottled water always increases in the range of 10% every year [1]. This is inseparable from the increase in population and increasing public awareness of the consumption of clean and quality drinking water as seen in the increase in the percentage of drinking water sources recorded by Statistics Indonesia, namely 89.27% in 2019, 90.21% in 2020, and 90.78% in 2021 [2]. The data provider agency Statista noted a rise in the volume of drinking water distribution in Indonesia. Approximately 4.35 billion cubic meters of drinking water in 2020 were distributed throughout Indonesia [3]. Even so, now there are still more than 20 million Indonesians who still lack access to an improved water source. PT Indofood CBP Sukses Makmur, a leading FMCG company, has a subsidiary that produces bottled water business with the brand "Club". With intense competition, the Club is able to compete with its competitors to successfully attract customers which are reflected in the percentage of its market share. According to Top Brand Indonesia (is a national-scale independent survey that is conducted annually by involving customers directly) There are five brands of bottled water that are chosen by customers, the first place is the Aqua brand with a total market share of 57.2%, the second is the Le Minerale brand with a market share percentage of 12.5%, the third is the Ades brand with a market share percentage of 6.4%, which the fourth is the Cleo brand with a market share percentage of 4.2% and the fifth is the Club brand with a market share percentage of 3.8% [4].

LITERATURE REVIEW

The strategy described by Thompson et al. is a form of coordination taken in order to outperform its competitors which ultimately achieves superior profitability. Thompson et al. further explains that the success of a strategy depends on the steps taken and carried out by a company in competing with its rivals to gain competitive advantages from them [5]. To create a successful strategy, a set of actions is needed to gain and sustain competitive advantages by doing 3 things: analyze, formulate, and implement what is captured in the AFI strategy framework [6]. Consumer behavior is strongly influenced by the circumstances and situations of the society in which he was born and developed. This means that consumers from different walks of life or environments will have different assessments, needs, opinions, attitudes, and tastes so the return of decisions in the purchase stage will be influenced by several factors which are cultural factors, social factors, personal factors, and psychological factors [7]. Some behavior also could influence intention and buying decision which are influence from other person, situational factor, social class, demography, and group influence [8]. With changes in lifestyle and high mobility, consumers tend to use more mineral water drinks every day. This is because there is a guarantee of cleanliness and health of mineral water products, in addition to that, consumers will benefit more from affordable prices and products that are practical to consume. Various considerations in the decision to buy mineral water products are influenced by several factors such as price, quality, brand, promotion, and distribution [9]. Based on previous research regarding the factors affecting Ghanaian consumers' purchasing decision of bottled water, shows that there is a significant relationship between demographic factors and psychological factors (such as perception and belief) in bottled water buying behavior. Furthermore, this study identifies four factors that influence respondents in buying bottled mineral water. These factors include quality, brand price, availability, and package [10]. Prior research related to on the impact of brand image on purchasing decisions on mineral water product "Amidis" shows that attributes, benefits, and attitudes are not positively influenced on purchasing decisions among buyers and potential buyers of mineral water "Amidis". However, the brand image of mineral water has positively influenced pricing decisions among buyers and potential buyers of "Amidis" mineral water [11]. Another research related to consumer purchase decision show that brand image and price influence the decision to purchase Aqua Bottled Drinking Water in the people of Surabaya. However, the packaging does not affect the purchasing decision of Aqua Packaged Drinking Water in the people of Surabaya. Brand image has a more significant influence than price and packaging on purchasing decisions [12]. Price is the only element in the marketing mix that generates sales revenue. This can be interpreted that with the right price producers can increase the demand for a product. But sometimes cutting prices is not the best answer because useless reducing prices can cause price wars and lead to lost profits [13]. Quality is a characteristic of a product that reflects the ability to meet predetermined and invisible needs. Quality in the view of consumers is something that has its own scope which is different from quality in the view of producers when issuing a product that is usually known for its true quality. Product quality is formed by several indicators, including ease of use, durability, clarity of function, variety, product size, and others [14]. Branding is the process of giving brand power to products services and creating differentiation between products. to create a strong brand, strategic brand management is needed which combines the design and implementation of marketing activities and programs to build, measure, and manage brands to maximize their value. Strategic brand management consists of four steps including identifying and establishing brand positioning; planning and implementing brand marketing; measuring and interpreting brand performance; growing and sustaining brand values [7]. Promotion is very important because apart from being able to build brand awareness, promotion can also increase brand trust which makes consumers interested in buying and repurchasing the products being sold. Promotion made to sell products is a key element in the company's campaign, and the best promotions are promotions done by satisfied customers. Thus, promotions need to be handled carefully because the problem is not only related to how to communicate with customers but also regarding how much money will be incurred by the company which of course must be adjusted to the conditions and capabilities of the company [15]. There are five major promotion mixes consisting of advertising, sales promotion, personal selling, public relations (PR) [13]. Distribution or distribution channels are a series of interdependent organizations that facilitate the transfer of ownership of products moving from producers to business users or customers [16]. Marketing activities related to products, pricing, and promotion, which are carried out cannot be said to be an integrated business if they are not complemented by distribution activities [17]. This research is aim to see if price, quality, brand, distribution, and promotion have impact on consumer purchase decision to buy mineral water. Therefore the framework in this study will examine the relationship between the independent variables (price, quality, brand, promotion, and distribution) to the dependent variable (purchasing decision), which further be used to determine the appropriate business strategy. Based on the theoretical basis discussed earlier, the conceptual framework used in this research is as **Figure 1.**

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

METHODOLOGY

This research is problem-solving research, based on the explanation and table above the respondent/sample size required in this study to answer the questionnaire is a minimum of 200 respondents and used a random sampling method [18]. In selecting respondents, the researcher uses the probability sample technique method where each item in the population has the same opportunity to be included in the sample [19]. To reach the respondents in multiple areas, the researcher distributed questionnaires using the internet, this was convenient and did not take up a lot of time. Researchers use a Likert scale in assessing respondents' answers, with the calculation of weight 5 for strongly agree, weight 4 for agree, weight 3 for enough, weight 2 for disagree, and weight 1 for strongly disagree [20]. The answers from the respondents were then analyzed using SPSS statistical data processing software to answer the following hypotheses:

- H1: Price has a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions
- H2: Quality has a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions
- H3: Brand has a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions
- H4: Promotion/advertisement has a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions
- H5: Distribution has a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Preliminary Analysis

Before conducting deep analysis, the researcher did a preliminary analysis by distributing questionnaires to 20 respondents randomly to find out the reasons for buying mineral water, the following is the result of the analysis:

Figure 2. Preliminary Analysis Result

The results of the analysis in Figure 2, show that there are three reasons for respondents to buy mineral water based on the highest percentage, with details: 35% of respondents bought mineral water because of the ease of buying products, 25% buying mineral

water because of the taste of the product suits the respondent's tastes, 15% buying mineral water because products offer added value compared to the competitors.

Root Cause Analysis

According to the preliminary analysis, further root cause analysis is carried out using the problem tree analysis. **Figure 3.** Possible root causes that could lead to a decline in Club mineral water sales include lack of cooperation with distribution seen from the availability of Clubs which have not been found around consumers; lack of utilization of digital platforms and lack of promotions; and the last possible root cause is lack of product innovation.

Figure 3. Problem Tree Analysis

Respondent's General Information

Respondent's general information consists of gender, age, occupation, mineral water brand information consumed daily, and exposure to Club brand mineral water products to the respondents. The respondent's general information results from 232 respondents are shown below:

A. Mineral water brand information consumed daily

Figure 4. Respondent's daily consumed of drinking water brand

According to **Figure 4**, the survey results showed there are five top brands, according to respondents, which first is mineral water with the Aqua brand (144 of 232 respondents or 49.1% consumed Aqua brand daily), the second place around 53 out of 232 respondents consumed mineral water with the brand Le Minerale (22.8%), third place 20 of 232 respondents (8.6%) consumed mineral water with the Cleo brand, fourth place 13 of 232 respondents (5.6%) consumed mineral water with Nestle Pure Life, and the fifth place 7 of 232 respondents (3.0%) consumed mineral water with Club brand. A small number of respondents chose refill gallons of mineral water (2.2%), Pristine (2.2%), Vit (2.2%), Crystalline (1.3%), Aklia (0.4%), Al Ain (0.4%), Biru (0.4%), Grand (0.4%), Oasis (0.4%), Oxy (0.4%), and Quavit (0.4%) for daily consumption.

B. Gender

Figure 5. The Respondent's Gender

From **Figure 5**, above, there were 115 male respondents (49.6%) and 117 female respondents (50.4%) with a total of 232 respondents, participated in filling out the research questionnaire.

C. Age

Figure 6. Respondent's Age

According to **Figure 6**, Respondent's ages in this study varied from <20 years to >55 years. The results of the questionnaire showed that the age group who filled out the questionnaire the most was in the age range of 26-35 years is 93 respondents (40.1%). The second place with an age range of 36-45 years is 51 respondents (22.0%). The third place with an age range of 46-55 years is 39 respondents (16.8%). Fourth place with an age range of 20-25 years as many as 25 respondents (10.8%). The fifth order with an age range of >55 years was 19 respondents (8.2%), and the last order with an age range of <20 years was 5 respondents (2.2%).

D. Occupation

Figure 7. Respondent's Occupation

Based on **Figure 7**, there are a total of 97 respondents from a total of 232 respondents (41.8%) work as government employees, 81 respondents (34.9%) work as private employees, 18 respondents (7.8%) are students/college students, and 16 respondents (6.9%) are entrepreneurs. The other percentage of 3.4%; 2.6%; 1.3%; 0.9%; 0.4% work as SOE employees, housewives, pastors, teachers, and personal trainees.

E. Exposure to Club Brand Mineral Water Products

Have you ever consumed Club brand mineral water before?

Figure 8. Respondent's Exposure to Club Mineral Water

Based on **Figure 8**, the survey results also showed that 200 out of 232 respondents (86.2%) had consumed Club brand mineral water, and another 32 respondents (13.8%) had not consumed Club brand mineral water.

F. Club Mineral Water Media Promotion

Figure 9. Club Mineral Water Promotion from The Eye of Respondent's

As can be seen from **Figure 69** the results of the questionnaire showed that 165 respondents (71.1%) had seen promotional activities conducted by Club brand mineral water through promotional media such as Social Media, TV & Radio, Billboards & Banners, Search Engine Ads, and Brochures & Booklets with details of 67 respondents (28.9%) respondents know about promotional activities through Social Media, 38 respondents (16.4%) know about promotional activities through TV & Radio, 18 respondents (7.8%) know about promotional activities through Search Engine Ads, 42 respondents (18.1%) know about promotional activities through a combination of two or more promotional media such as Social Media, TV & Radio, Billboards & Banners, Search Engine Ads, and/or Brochures & Booklets. Meanwhile, 26 respondents (11.2%) know Club mineral water from supermarket displays instead of through promotional media, and 41 respondents (17.7%) had never seen Club brand mineral water promotional activities.

Consumer Analysis

For the 200 respondents who answered "had consumed Club mineral water", has conducted a statistical analysis to see whether there was an influence on price (X1), quality (X2), brand (X3), promotion (X4), and distribution (X4) factors on the purchase decision (Y) which can be seen in the following detailed explanation.

A. Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Table 1. Multiple Linear Analysis

Model	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
(Constant)	.236	.763		.309	.758
Price (X1)	.447	.096	.248	4.653	.000
Quality (X2)	.208	.054	.288	3.847	.000
Brand (X3)	.258	.091	.209	2.830	.005
Promotion (X4)	.151	.050	.151	3.040	.003
Distribution (X5)	.107	.049	.109	2.176	.031

$$Y = a + bX_1 + bX_2 + bX_3 + bX_4 + bX_5 + e$$

$$Y = 0.236 + 0.447X_1 + 0.208X_2 + 0.258X_3 + 0.151X_4 + 0.107X_5 + e$$

According to **Table 1.** and equation above it can be explained if the constant is positive 0.236 meaning that if the variables X1 to X5 are zero (0) or the value is fixed (constant), then variable Y has a value of 0.236. In other words, the higher the (X1) – (X5), the higher the level of purchasing decisions. It also shows that H1 – H5 has a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions, in other words, H0 is rejected and H1 – H5 is accepted.

B. F (simultaneous) Test

Table 2. F (simultaneous) Test

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	2091.327	5	418.265	119.707	.000 ^b
Residual	677.853	194	3.494		
Total	2769.180	199			

a. Dependent Variable: Purchase Decision (Y)

b. Predictors: (Constant), Distribution (X5), Promotion (X4), Price (X1), Brand (X3), Quality (X2)

F-Table = (n-k) = (200-5) = F-Table 195 = 2.26

Based on **Table 2.** above it is known that the calculated F value is greater than the F table (119,707 > 2.26), with a significance value of 0.000 < 0.05. This shows that there is a simultaneous influence of the variables Price (X1), Quality (X2), Brand (X3), Promotion (X4), and Distribution (X5) on the purchasing decision variable (Y).

C. Determination Test

Table 3. Determination Test

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.869 ^a	.755	.749	1.86925

Predictors: (Constant), Distribution (X5), Promotion (X4), Price (X1), Brand (X3), Quality (X2)

From the **Table 3.** above it can be seen that the R Square value is 0.755 or 75.5%. This value indicates the influence of the variables X1 to X5 on the combined Y variable, while the remaining 24.5% is influenced by other variable factors outside this study or the error value.

SWOT Analysis

A SWOT analysis can help determine whether a strategy has been effective in fending off external threats and positioning the firm to take advantage of market opportunities [5]. SWOT will then analyze Club Strength [21], Weakness, Opportunity, and Threat. The results of the SWOT analysis can be seen in the following Table.

Table 4. SWOT Analysis Result

Strength	Weakness
Under the establish parent company (Indofood) meaning that Club mineral water has strong investors to support its financial Mature organization, therefore the company had wide connection Strong R&D division High-tech production machine Have a distribution channel (as part of Indofood Group, Club mineral water could get benefit to distribute its product through Indomarco)	Promotion/socialization activities have not been maximized Product availability is still minimal / relatively Bottles used as packaging can cause waste There are no competitive advantages offered by the product compared to competitors

Has many factories spread throughout Indonesia The price offered tends to be cheaper	
Opportunity	Threat
Economies of scale Acquisition to create new products Join with other companies that have similar products Through marketing team create promos to attract customers Utilizing digital platforms to promote products Creates product innovations that have not existed in the market before	Threat from new entrants Products are easy to imitate by rivals Club mineral water is at a perfect competitive market and leads to price war between sellers Government regulation Intense competition by competitors in terms of advertising and innovation

Proposed Business Strategy

1. Doing a joint venture with a company that has a similar business to develop new product
Club mineral water as a subsidiary of an established and well-known FMCG company can attract other companies to collaborate in creating new products. Previously the Club had collaborated with PT Ashai in terms of developing production machine facilities, this strategy could be carried out again by the Club such as working with an AI company to help the company improve its production activities.
2. Collaborate with social media content creators and web designers to introduce products digitally
Club mineral water as part of the FMCG business will continue to be present in offline stores. However, with the development of technology in this digitalization era, Clubs are required to be able to improve their online presence with better websites and more efficient and effective use of various social media platforms through initiatives movements. The club itself already uses official social media platforms such as Instagram and websites. However, social media and websites have not been used optimally. For Instagram social media, for example, Club Instagram's official pages show that the promotional activities have not been actively carried out through posts made on Instagram when compared to its competitors. As for the website, the Club's website is still standard in shape and tends not to be informative, including every event or program that is being carried out on the website page.
3. Utilize existing resources to innovate products
With the resources and capabilities that the Club has, such as a strong R&D division and a high technology production machine, the Club should be able to use it to carry out product development to create new mineral water product innovations that its competitors do not yet have.
4. Actively conduct product R&D and introduce it to the public
Seeing the threat from fellow players in this industry demands that Club mineral water should analyze the market to find out market needs and wants. From this analysis, it is hoped that Club mineral water will be able to find out the niche market that is under-served by its competitors. Furthermore, for products that are successfully developed, the Club introduces them to the public more often so that the market is aware of every product development carried out by the Club.
5. Utilizing and maximizing factories that spread across all areas in Indonesia to sell best quality products
Club mineral water has 19 factories spread across Indonesia so it has a distinct advantage for the Club to cover a wider market. With this advantage, the Club can set a strategy for its production results so the Club's mineral water can be widely spread throughout Indonesia. It is hoped that from this strategy the Club can become a market leader in the bottled drinking water market due to the availability of products and the convenience for consumers to buy products wherever they are.
6. Conduct product marketing to the public through digital platforms, events, or programs
This strategy can be carried out by utilizing digital platforms to promote their products such as optimizing engagement on Instagram through ads, utilizing search engine ads (Google Ads), placing advertisements in public places and public transportation (such as commuter line carriages, MRT or buses), participating in various small and large events, collaborating with influencers, or carrying out some campaigns related to the importance of consuming mineral water.
7. Innovates "green products" with different formulations, or other innovations and announces it to the public through digital platforms to get attention

People are now starting to change their habits, one of which is switching habits to using green products. A green product is a product that is friendly or harmless to the environment, either during the production process or when consuming it. Club mineral water product doesn't have eco-friendly products yet. This can be a strategy for the Club to make green products such as developing biodegradable packaging with the latest formulations that are easy to recycle. Furthermore, Club mineral water products can also innovate in terms of labeling and packaging so that the products offer different values to the customers.

8. Analyze factories and distributors spread throughout Indonesia to find out whether they are optimal in producing and selling products. As well as conducting product and market analysis to determine the company's position

To ensure whether the sales are optimal or not, the Club needs to carry out an internal workflow analysis at the 19 factories. End-to-end process analysis, namely analysis from receiving raw materials to finished products, quality checking process, cash receipts-spending process, including human resources, product, and asset inventory analysis needs to be conducted to find out whether each department in the factory has worked and carried out operational activities effectively and efficiently. Next, do a market analysis to see consumer attractiveness.

9. Analyze the company's potential, clarify its strength, and collaborate with universities to gain ideas or insight to innovate.

Club mineral water needs to do a deeper analysis to find the company's potential so they can determine the strengths that lead them to have a competitive advantage. Apart from that, the Club can also collaborate with university students not only to promote the Club brand but also to get business insights by conducting Club open innovation for university students to discuss innovation in bottled water, or how to improve marketing strategy for instance with university students.

CONCLUSION

The results of this analysis indicate that there has been no product innovation carried out by Club mineral water products when compared to their competitors. In addition, there is still a lack of utilization of digital media to promote its mineral water products. Even though Club is one of the brands chosen by consumers, there are still many consumers who don't know the Club mineral water brand. With recommendations for collaborating with influencers, conducting joint ventures with similar companies, utilizing existing resources to innovate products, actively conducting product R&D and introducing it to the public, innovating "green products" with different formulations, analyzing the company's potential, clarifying its strength, and collaborate with universities (such as business schools) to gain ideas or insight to innovate, it is hoped that this will become a solution to increase sales of the Club's mineral water products.

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